

Trends of educational innovation in the higher education of Latin America

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Abstract

Latin America has made progress in meeting Sustainable Development Goal (SDG) 4 on quality education; however, only six countries in the region met SDG 4 by 2022. The fulfillment of SDG 4 implies improving access and quality indicators at different educational levels in each country, so it is expected that the country that meets it will present high levels of educational innovation. However, not all educational changes represent educational innovations, so a literature review was conducted to delimit the meaning of educational innovation in Latin America. The Systematic Literature Review (SLR) asked the research question What is known about educational innovation in Latin America? The SLR protocol includes three phases: plan, review, and report the results of 51 selected papers. The obtained definition of educational innovation was as a transformation that requires reflection on the feasibility and relevance of the change, which could satisfy the needs identified before the introduction of the change and imply leaving the comfort zone, thus requiring continuous learning. The results made it possible to delimit the meaning, benefits, and different approaches to educational innovations, and to understand the role of the teacher as an agent promoting change in their teaching practices and the student's learning experience.

Keywords: Educational Innovation; Access to education; SDG 4; Education; Latin America.

1 Introduction

The SDG Index of the Center for Sustainable Development Goals for Latin America and the Caribbean (CODS) measures compliance with the 2030 Agenda for Sustainable Development in the Latin American region, following the Sustainable Development Solutions Network methodology (UNSDSN, n.d.), validated by the European Commission (Sachs et al., 2019).

Since 2015, Latin America has shown more lags than goals met in the 17 Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs). Most countries in the region have not met SDG 4 on quality education, which is measured through five indicators that evaluate access to all levels of education in each country. The five indicators are the average net enrollment rate in primary education, the lower secondary school completion rate, the literacy rate for both sexes aged 15-24, the gross enrollment rate in tertiary education, and the gross enrollment rate in preschool education. (Sánchez-Gómez, 2023).

However, SDG 4 continues to lag at the regional level, reaching a score of 55.33 in 2022, below 58.65, which is the average score of all 17 SDGs in the region. Therefore, only 6 Latin American countries have achieved SDG 4, such as Argentina, Chile, Costa Rica, Mexico, Peru, and Uruguay, while the other countries in the region are lagging.

In this context, education requires that the different actors in the sector be agents of change, through the development of educational innovations that improve quality. In this task, teachers are expected to take the lead in these educational innovations. Still, it is also expected that to improve the quality of education, teachers should be well-trained.

For this reason, teacher training becomes the starting point for the design, implementation, and evaluation of educational innovations, since good training in research and innovation allows the development of relevant and sustainable innovations over time.

A systematic literature review was conducted to delimit the definition of educational innovation in Latin America, to understand its transformative meaning not only in the teaching role but also in the learning experience of students.

2 Methodology

A systematic literature review was used to identify and assess the validity of important studies that answer the research question (Brettel, 2003). Therefore, this study seeks to answer the question of what is known about educational innovation in Latin America. In this sense, the review aims to summarize relevant information on educational innovation as the topic of interest of this research (Cruz-Lemus, 2014). A selection of documents from different sources of information was included, including papers from indexed journals and conference papers. The review was carried out through three phases: plan, review, and report, following the methodology of (Kitchenham et al., 2007).

2.1 Planning

The first planning phase seeks to identify the needs of the review, formulate the research question, and define the review protocol. The review's objective was to identify the different definitions given to the concept of educational innovation in the literature, which is why we formulated the question: What is known about educational innovation in Latin America?

The literature review protocol involves defining search and evaluation criteria to limit the scope of the review to select the documents that best answer the research question.

The search criteria (see Table 1) allowed us to define the inclusion parameters at the time of the search in different sources of information.

Table 1. Search criteria.

Criteria	Description
Language	Spanish and English.
Publication year	From 1995.
Keywords	Innovación educativa, educational innovation.
Type of papers	Refereed papers, conference papers, and books.
Databases consulted	Google Scholar, Springer, Scielo, Taylor & Francis Online, Elsevier, Redalyc y Dialnet.

The evaluation criteria (see Table 2) made it possible to analyze the importance of the documents according to their level of contribution. The prestige criteria are related to the h-index of the author and journal, like 1 point for an h-index between 10 and 29 and 2 points for an h-index upper to 30. The abstract was evaluated in terms of clarity of the problem and the solution proposed and their pertinence for this study. The method was evaluated as 2 points for papers with aligned research questions, approach, and methods, and 1 point for papers without these consistencies. The results were evaluated as 2 points for the paper with obtained data and information related to each research question, objectives, and methods, and 1 point for papers without these coherencies.

Therefore, each document found was analyzed with the five evaluation criteria, assigning a value from 0 to 2 points for each criterion, with 0 points for low-contribution documents, 1 point for medium-contribution documents, and 2 points for high-contribution documents.

Table 2. Evaluation criteria.

Criteria	Contribution	Description
Journal/Editorial	0-2 points	Prestige of the journal/editorial.
Authors	0-2 points	Prestige of the authors.
Consistency	0-2 points	Consistency of abstract.
Method	0-2 points	Methodological design
Results	0-2 points	Relevance of the results.
TOTAL	10 points	

2.2 Review

In the review phase, the protocol designed in the previous phases is implemented, thus, the relevant documents found in the literature are obtained. First, 51 relevant documents were identified in the seven databases consulted: Google Scholar, Springer, Scielo, Taylor & Francis Online, Elsevier, Redalyc, and Dialnet.

To evaluate the level of contribution of each document, the contribution value assigned to each criterion (journal, author, coherence, appropriateness, and results) was summed, totaling a maximum of 10 points.

Each document was given a final score according to its low, medium, or high level of contribution (see Table 3). From the total of 51 documents, 21 were selected with a high contribution level obtaining a final score of 9 to 10 points, 16 documents with medium contribution obtaining a score of 7 to 8 points, 5 documents with low contribution obtaining a score of 4 to 6 points) and 9 documents were discarded for obtaining a very low score of 0 to 3 points.

Table 3. Documents by contribution level.

Contribution	Quantity	Percentage
Discarded	9	18%
Low	5	10%
Medium	16	31%
High	21	41%
TOTAL	51	100%

Given that it is necessary to define a definition of educational innovation, which should synthesize the most important definitions in the literature, only documents with a high level of contribution were selected, i.e., those documents that obtained a final score of 9 or more points.

These 21 selected documents (see Table 4) were mostly refereed papers (76%), followed by conference papers (15%) and books (10%).

Table 4. Selected documents.

Type	Quantity	Percentage
Refereed papers	16	76%
Conference papers	3	15%
Books	2	10%
TOTAL	21	100%

2.3 Report

To identify the gaps in the literature, the proposed research question was answered by extracting the relevant data from the 21 selected documents to synthesize different ideas that made it possible to delimit the concept of educational innovation.

A thematic analysis was made of the main ideas of the 21 selected documents, which allowed the classification of these ideas into major themes. These major themes shape the trends in the literature, revealing the possible gaps in the literature on these topics.

3 Results

The results of this literature review allowed us to obtain a delimited definition, and understand its benefits and approaches to educational innovation.

3.1 Delimited definition of educational innovation

Several elements can be summarized from the above definitions. First, an educational innovation is a transformation that requires reflection on the feasibility and relevance of the change. Second, an educational innovation could satisfy the needs that were identified before the introduction of the change. Thirdly, an educational innovation implies leaving the comfort zone, thus requiring continuous learning.

However, to identify whether educational innovation is promoted in high-quality accreditation, the definition needs to be further refined. In this regard, according to (Navarro, 2000) innovation should be understood as a deliberate action with a prior planning of its objectives, a planned change that is neither spontaneous nor free, and it requires inquiring into its effects, impact, and appropriation in the educational community.

3.2 Benefits of an educational innovation

Understanding an educational innovation as a change allows generating opportunities for transformation in the educational sector, focused on improving the quality of the educational service. However, to improve the quality of education, good teacher training is required, through training in research and evaluation of educational innovations, promoting educational change through these innovations (Cifuentes, 2018).

In addition, an educational innovation makes it possible to ensure the rational use of ICTs for teaching (Bates, 2015) in engineering (Galvis et al., 2019), according to the learning styles (Entwistle, 2001) and reflection as a teaching and learning method (Durgahee, 1998).

Likewise, an educational innovation makes it possible to take advantage of face-to-face and virtual education modalities in a hybrid modality (Garrison & Kanuka, 2004), use of autonomous time and classroom time through the flipped classroom (Baytiyeh & Naja, 2017).

Finally, educational innovations promote the use of active methodologies in interactive classes with large groups and learning at any time and place (Salinas Ibáñez, 2003).

3.3 Approaches of Educational Innovation

An educational innovation can be understood from three approaches: as a change, as the introduction of a new element, or as a learning process (Cifuentes, 2018).

The first approach describes educational innovation as a change involving a transformation (Hargreaves, 2002), i.e., a change in conceptions, practices, and resources (Salinas, 2004). The change brought about by educational innovation (Fullan, 2002), is planned and guided toward improvement (Navarro, 2000), that meets the specific needs of the educational context.

The second approach refers to an educational innovation as something new, i.e., the introduction of a new product or process (Renzulli, 2003). The novelty of the educational innovation depends on the reference that exists in the educational context in which it is intended to be implemented. The introduction of this novelty can be external or internal, depending on the agent that proposes the introduction of the change (Navarro, 2000).

The third approach presents educational innovation as a learning process, which implies leaving the "comfort zone" and control. This learning consists of experiencing innovation as an unstable and uncertain process, which can be learned by observing and reflecting on the educational context in which it takes place (Kolb, 2014).

4 Conclusions

The literature review protocol made it possible to follow each of the phases of the process step by step. However, the protocol should continue to be validated, to continue replicating it in future research, especially those that do not have a geographical delimitation, as in this case it was done with the Latin American region. This region was selected due to the strong influence and dominance of research from the Global North, which does not allow us to know the positions and trends in the Latin American region. For this reason, special relevance was given to those documents whose authors and objects of study were related to Latin America.

The results showed that the trends of educational innovation in Latin America are related to its conceptualization, its potential benefits in different case studies, as well as theoretical discussions regarding the different approaches that educational innovations can take. However, there are gaps regarding methodological designs, methods, and good practices to successfully develop an educational innovation.

Finally, this literature review contributes to the meeting of SDG 4 for clarities about the meaning of educational innovation and to promote their design and implementation in different educational contexts in Latin America. SDG 4 seeks to guarantee access to quality education, but this quality requires best teaching practices and their continued improvement through educational innovations (Sánchez-Gómez, 2024).

In future work, it is expected to focus the literature review on the methodological aspects, to fill these gaps in the literature and provide guidelines and tools for teachers to validate these instruments, through the development of educational innovations that transform their teaching practices.

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